

5-Hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone from *Cheilanthes farinosa* Kaulf. (Cheilanthaceae)[†]

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Manuscript received 10 August 2007, revised 18 January 2008, accepted 21 January 2008

Abstract : *Cheilanthes farinosa* Kaulf. (Cheilanthaceae) has been established as new source of the natural flavonoid, 5-hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone, characterized on the basis of spectral studies.

Keywords : *Cheilanthes farinosa*, Cheilanthaceae, 5-hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone, spectral studies.

Introduction

At the present scenario of drug research, bio-flavonoids are being considered as useful and promising leads due to their multidirectional therapeutic efficacies, very particularly as antioxidant and anticancerous agents^{1,2}. This remarkable class of plant secondary metabolites also exhibits a wide range of biological activities². In continuation of our works on medicinal plants, we have found *Cheilanthes farinosa* Kaulf. (family : Cheilanthaceae) as a new source of 5-hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone, a well-known natural flavonol derivative^{3,4}.

C. farinosa is a small tufted fern very common in the hilly regions⁵. The plant has been traditionally used in the treatment of various diseases. Ethanol extract (50%) of the fern has been found to be spasmolytic and CNS depressant; fronds of the plant are used in the seasonal fever⁶. The paste of fronds and rhizomes along with turmeric is applied for skin diseases⁷. The plant also finds wide applications to treat inflammatory skin disorders; the fronds have been evaluated to possess strong *in vivo* anti-inflammatory and anti-nociceptive properties⁸. Clinical and haematological studies on *C. farinosa* using rat models were also reported by Sekaran *et al.*⁹. Isolations of only a few chemical constituents from this plant have been reported earlier^{8,10,11}.

(1)

5-Hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone

Results and discussion

The monohydroxy-trimethoxy flavone **1**, C₁₈H₁₆O₆ ([M]⁺ at *m/z* 328), responded positively toward flavonoid colour reactions and ferric chloride solution, and exhibited characteristic UV absorptions at λ_{max} (MeOH) 270 and 335 nm. The infrared absorption bands of **1** are also of expected outcome – appearance of the absorption band at 3450.3 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum denotes the bonded hydroxyl, while the absorption bands at 1657.2, 1586.1, 1501.6 and 1433.5 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of an α,β-unsaturated carbonyl function attached with aromatic nucleus. In the ¹H NMR spectrum of flavonoid **1**, we observed three separate signals due to three methoxy groups (linked with aromatic nucleus), for the first time in this molecule, at δ 3.901 (3H, s), 3.875 (3H, s) and 3.866 (3H, s); we also observed for the first time in **1** that the B-ring protons appeared as double doublets (dd)

[†]The work has been presented in the INDO-US Conference on New Bioactive Molecules in Pharmaceutical Research : Contribution of Natural Products. November 13-14, 2006. IICT, Hyderabad, India.

– δ 8.077 (2H, dd, J 1.95, 9.03 Hz, H-2' and H-6') and 7.025 (2H, dd, J 1.95, 9.03 Hz, H-3' and H-5') – thereby supporting the proposed B-ring substitution pattern. It is also evidenced from the ^1H NMR spectrum that C-3 position is blocked by one of the substituents.

The mass spectral fragmented ion-peaks of compound **1** clearly suggest that one methoxyl and one hydroxyl functions are attached to the ring-A, while the remaining two methoxyls are linked with the ring-B and C-3 position. The B-ring methoxyl is unambiguously located at C-4' as evidenced from the ^1H NMR spectral analysis. Again, the appearance of intense green colour with ferric chloride imparted by the compound locates the A-ring hydroxyl at C-5 position¹² as also revealed from the IR and ^1H NMR spectra. The two A-ring aromatic protons appeared as *meta*-coupled in the ^1H NMR spectrum at δ 6.44 (1H, d, J 2.17 Hz) and 6.35 (1H, d, J 2.17 Hz) indicating, thereby, the location of the remaining methoxy group at C-7. Hence, the monohydroxy-trimethoxyflavone (**1**) has been characterized as 5-hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone.

Experimental

Air-dried defatted powdered whole plants (1.5 kg) of *Cheilanthes farinosa* Kaulf. were extracted with petrol (60–80°) in a Soxhlet apparatus for 56 h. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and then subjected to column chromatography on silica gel (60–120 mesh, 200 g); the benzene : chloroform (1 : 1) eluent afforded 5-hydroxy-3,7,4'-trimethoxyflavone as yellow solid (yield 600 mg), m.p. 145 °C (uncorrected); UV (methanol) : λ_{max} 270, 335 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} : 3450.3, 3085.9, 2931.5, 2849.7, 1657.2, 1586.1, 1501.6, 1433.5, 1341, 1218, 1172.9, 1028.3, 871.2 and 829 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 500 MHz; TMS) : δ 12.66 (1H, s, HO-5), 8.077 (2H, dd, J 1.95, 9.03 Hz, H-2' and H-6') and 7.025 (2H, dd, J 1.95, 9.03 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 6.44 (1H, d, J 2.17 Hz, H-6), 6.35 (1H, d, J 2.17 Hz, H-8), 3.901 (3H, s, CH_3O -3), 3.875 (3H, s, CH_3O -7) and 3.866 (3H, s, CH_3O -4'); EIMS (70 eV) : m/z 328 ($[\text{M}]^+$, base peak), 313 [$\text{M}-\text{Me}]^+$, 300 [$\text{M}-\text{CO}]^+$, 298 [$\text{M}-2\text{Me}]^+$, 285 [$\text{M}-\text{CO}-$

$\text{Me}]^+$, 166 and 162 (retro-Diels-Alder fragmented ion peaks), 138 [$166-\text{CO}]^+$, 137 [$138-\text{H}]^+$, 135 (fragmented ion peak), 131 [$162-\text{OMe}]^+$, 123 [$138-\text{Me}]^+$, 120 [$135-\text{Me}]^+$.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from UGC, New Delhi [Project No. F.32-152/2005 (SR)] is deeply acknowledged. The authors are also grateful to RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow for spectral measurements.

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